

Impact of the use of ChatGPT AI Tool on Students' Academic Performance

Oderonke Odeniyi¹, Emmanuel Tolufase² and Kolawole Adeyemo³

¹Computer Science Department, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano

²Physics Department, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano

³Mathematics Department, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano

Abstract-: AI tools are useful and of great importance in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Their usefulness cannot be overemphasized as Lecturers and students use them to find timely solutions to their academic related problems. This research work is centered on assessing the impact of the use of Chat GPT AI tool as against other AI tools on the overall performance of university students (undergraduates) in Northern Nigeria with a focus on cadets of the Nigeria Police Academy, Kano from five different departments : Physics Chemistry, Biology, Mathematics and Computer Science departments. A total of 250 respondents was targeted . The survey used Google form as a survey tool and then distribution was done via email. Data from the Google form was retrieved in Google sheets, Cleaned, Processed and Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) was done in GoogleColab IDE using Python Programming Language. The results from this work shows that cadets use ChatGPT AI tool way more than any other AI tool for their assignments, research work and even online purchases .

Keywords: AI(Artificial Intelligence), VR(Virtual Reality), AR(Augmented Reality) SM(Social Media), GPT(Generative Pre- trained Transformer), GAN(Generator and Discriminator Networks)

Email: odeniyironke@gmail.com

Received: February 1, 2024

Revised: March 4, 2024

Accepted: March 20, 2024

Cite this paper as: Oderonke, O., Emmanuel, T., & Kolawole, A. (2024, March 30). Effect of the use of ChatGPT AI Tool on Students' Academic Performance. *Science Journal of Applied and Natural Sciences (SJANS)*, 3(1), 1-11.

About the Journal: SJANS is a multidisciplinary science journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

The use of Artificial Intelligence tools has become very rampant among individuals globally as a result of the fact that it makes accessing information, processing data as well as dissemination of important information a lot faster and easier.

Artificial Intelligence tools are used in virtually every facet of life. They are also commonly used by students worldwide in their academic work for projects and assignments as well as for recreation as seen in VR, Gaming, AR etc. Artificial Intelligence has impacted positively in diverse sectors globally and the education sector is not left out with the introduction of diverse AI tools such as Quizlet, Grammarly, Quillbot as well as MOOCs which are used for learning and self-development. ChatGPT is one of the very many AI tools used in higher education by both lecturers and students.

(Chassignol, M., Khoroshavin, A., Klimova, A., & Bilyatdinova, A. 2018) Artificial Intelligence, AI

is the field of computer science dedicated to solving cognitive problems commonly associated with human intelligence, such as learning, problem-solving, and pattern recognition. AI is —the theory and development of computer systems able to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation between languages. I

Lecturers in institutions of higher learning have adopted the use of different AI tools in making teaching easy for themselves as well as easing learning for their students (Chen, L., Chen, P., & Lin, Z. 2020). Students make up the larger population of AI tool users use these tools to carry out various tasks ranging from gaming and Virtual Reality (VR), generating social media content, creating beautiful art pieces to academic learning.

According to (Božić, V. n.d..) diverse tools have been adopted by university students to make learning a lot simpler and easy to follow but Chat GPT happens to be more commonly used in different parts of the world.

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

There are a large number of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs)[1] for the online study such as coursera.com. The growing amount of activate users of MOOCs courses shows that the electronic and distance learning methodologies are appreciated by the society. And some of the courses can give students a real opportunity to get official degree of some distinct and very respectable university. At the same time, we can observe recent advances of Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its application to educational process. For example, in neurosurgery, VR technologies already have a serious impact - 3D Oculus Surgical Theater is used for simulating surgery process of removing brain tumors

1.1 Literature Review

In accordance to (Chen, L., Chen, P., & Lin, Z. 2020), the study seeks to assess the impact of AI on education. More particularly, it seeks to ascertain how AI has affected education, looking at various aspects of education, including administration, instruction, and learning. This study takes a retrogressive approach, entailing assessing secondary data and materials or studies that have been undertaken while this research is centred on the impact of AI on learning; academic excellence to be precise (Aregbesola, B. G., Ojelade, I. A., Haastrup, D. T., & Nyinebi, M. 2024).

The study examined artificial intelligence creative compliance, and the future of science education: a study of Nigerian universities lecturers. An online cross-sectional questionnaire survey among science education lecturers were used across federal universities in five states and the Federal Capital Territory(FCT),Abuja.The survey used Google Forms as the survey tool and WhatsApp as the distribution platform. (Sahar Qaadani, A., Ammouri, M., Elashi, M., Abbad, W., & Alalamie, S. n.d..) This paper presents a dataset collected from students at an applied university in Jordan to understand their usage and perception of AI tools, specifically chatbots like ChatGPT and Bard, in their educational processes. The dataset is derived from a questionnaire that consists of two main sections while this work sheds light on various AI tools and their impact on the scores attained by the police cadets (students). Sahoo, K., Samal, A. K., Pramanik, J., & Pani, S. K. (2019).

Exploratory data analysis was carried out by using libraries like Pandas, Matplotlib and Seaborn to analyze amazon review datasets which contain review of electronic data items.

(Nongthombam, K., & Sharma, D. n.d)The dataset —World Happiness Report 2021I was used to analyze and extract various information in both numerical and pictorial form.(Izunna Somadina, O., & Olabisi, S. 2024.) The findings of the study reveal a prevalent use of AI technologies in education in Nigeria, encompassing evolutionary software modeling, student performance prediction, multimedia e-learning platforms and frameworks, and the incorporation of Moodle learning.

2.0 Materials and Methods

This research made use of Google Form in collecting primary data from cadets from seven different department (Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Maths, Computer Science , Biochemistry and Forensic Science) of divided into Nigeria PoliceAcademy. The form is in three (3)sections : The first section(Section A) is Demographics where information such as Age, Department , Level and CGPA were captured. The second section(Section B) is centered on the usage of ChatGPT and other AI tools by cadets. The third section (Section C) highlights Perceived Effect Of The Use Of ChatGPT And Other AI Tools On Students' Academic Performance. Email was used as a medium for the distribution of the questionnaire . Google-Colab was used as an IDE for the writing of the Python program because it makes it easy to incorporate other Google services such as Google Cloud Support, Google Drive and Google Sheets. It also permits a free cloud-based environment which makes coding easy and seamless. Google Colab is preferable for this project because of its support of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) and Tensor Processing Units (TPUs) which is of essence when working on Exploratory Data Analysis, Machine Learning and Deep Learning Project

2.1 Methodology

In this study, some research questions happen to be the driving forces. They are:

- How useful is the ChatGPT AI tool in effectively solving students' academic problems?
- 3.0 What significance is the use of ChatGPT on students' academic work?
- 4.0 How familiar are students with the use of different AI tools?
- 5.0 How efficient are the results generated from ChatGPT?
- 6.0 In what ways can ChatGPT foster academic integrity?

Key:

- A = Chat GPT AI Tool
- B = Cadets' Academic Performance
- C = Improved Learning
- D=Improved Curiosity for Knowledge Acquisition
- E = Good CGPA
- F = Improved Research

The figure above clearly shows that cadets who use ChatGPT AI tool for their academic work ended up improving their learning capability .It makes learning a lot simplified and concise. Secondly, it unleashed the cadets curiosity to acquire new knowledge as it exposed them to a much seamless output which can be further streamlined if the generated information is not favourable. Thirdly, cadets who use ChatGPT have considerably better CGPA compared with those who do not use ChatGPT. Lastly, ChatGPT users amongst the cadets are observed to be better at critical thinking which in turn improved their capability to carry out research.

Exploratory Data Analysis(EDA) was carried out using Python Programming because it is a multipurpose object oriented programming language which supports statistical computing with different packages and functions.

(Wes Mckinney,*Python*,2012)The following Python libraries were used for this project:

*Numpy: A short form for Numerical Python. It provides functions for carrying out element-wise computations with arrays or mathematical computations between arrays

*Pandas: provides functions and rich data structures' which makes working with structured data expressive, easy and fast. It uses `_DataFrame`' which comes in two dimensional tabular form i.e rows and columns *Matplotlib: is used for producing plots and other 2D-visualizations .It provides an interactive environment for plotting and exploring data.

2.2 Data Analysis Phases

When carrying out Data Analysis, there are five (5) phases involved. They include but are not limited to:

i. **Data Requirements:** In this work ,details such as the cadet's department, level, CGPA, Frequency of use of ChatGPT and many more were captured in order to assess the impact of ChatGPT AI tool on the overall academic performance of the cadet.

ii. **Data Collection:** Data was collected using a Google form(structured in form of a questionnaire) which is an online cloud resource which students/cadets can fill and submit . The questionnaire is composed of three (3) sections namely: Section A: Demographics, Section B: Usage of ChatGPT and other AI tools, Section C: Perceived Effect of the Use of ChatGPT and other AI tools on Students' Academic Performance

iii. **Data Processing :** The data collected for this research was processed and organized for analysis using Google sheets. It involved arranging the data in table format called **Structured Data** for further analysis.

v. **Exploratory Data Analysis:** After cleaning the data and certifying they are error-free, they can then be analyzed. iv. **Data Cleaning:** The data used for this research was scanned for inconsistencies , errors and duplicates and they were all removed. Data cleaning entails data quality maintenance, identifying data inaccuracy,record matching ,outlier data identification,textual data spell checker and data sorting.

2.3 Datasets

This data set was extracted from the survey questionnaire (in Google sheet) into Google sheets and later converted into a CSV file. A total of 1500 respondents were targeted but only 1085 respondents were gotten. After data

cleaning, the total became 1000. The column headers: S/N, Gender, Age, Department, Level/Regular, Course, CGPA etc

3.0 Libraries

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```


mydata=pd.read_csv(—AI TOOLS.csv) mydata

After importing the Python libraries as earlier stated, the data is then uploaded and read into the IDE.

Data Cleaning

This involves deleting null values or data from the records.

#isnull() returns true in the entry where there isn't any or a NaN value.

Sum() is used together with isnull() to find the total number of null values in each of the columns.
Mydata.isnull().sum()

Data Extraction

The top rows of this data set was extracted . To do this, the # head() was used while To extract the bottom rows, #tail() command was used .

In this case, to extract the first 15 rows of the dataset, use the following command:

headdata=mydata.head(15 headdata

While to extract the last 15rows of a dataset,

taildata=mydata.tail(15) taildata

To list the data types in the dataset,

mydata.dtypes

While to describe the entire dataset,

mydata.describe()

Finding the correlation between variables in the dataset, for the entire data **mydata.corr()**

PLEASE NOTE: As the time this research was conducted, 100Level (Regular Course 10) cadets had not written any examinations talk more of having CGPAs. So, no information as regards their CGPAs could be collated at this time.

FIGURE 1

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

FIGURE 2

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

FIGURE 3

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

FIGURE 4

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.

4.0 Results and Discussion

Python codes in Google Colab using Exploratory Data Analysis was used to plot the graphs in Figures 1 to 4 using the matplotlib library function. The blue bars clearly show CGPA of cadets who use ChatGPT while the orange bars show the CGPAs of cadets who do not use ChatGPT. The x-axis shows the groups of the different cadets depending on their levels (200level to 500level excluding 100level) while the y-axis shows the CGPAs of the two categories of cadets

From the graphs , it can be clearly seen that Cadets who used ChatGPT for their academic work performed better than those who did not. This is not to rule out the efficacy of other AI tools but to show that relatively, compared with

other AI tools such as Gemini, Grammarly, Quillbot Etc ChatGPT is the most sought after and has positive impact on the academic performance of cadets

5.0 Conclusion

The use of AI tools is still not very popular in some sectors and some persons still claim not to have used them before even academics and students.Hence the need for government regulatory bodies to inform and sensitize the citizenry on the importance of the use of AI tools.

There is also this misconception that AI has come to take up the jobs of some persons. This is a myth which is totally untrue. Rather,AI has come to simplify tasks, get jobs done faster and make life a lot better for people.For future work,

It is hereby recommended that they explore more AI tools and how they can be of essence .

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Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

Wes Mckinney, *Python for Data Analysis* "O'Reilly Media, Inc.", 8 Oct 2012
ISBN 1449323618, 9781449323615
<https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2023.6.2.36>